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KICHIK YOSHDAGI O'QUVCHILARGA TIL O'QITISHDA KOMMUNIKATIV YONDASHUV

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola til o'qitishga kommunikativ yondashuv uslubiga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, bu uslubning afzalliklarini ko'rsatib beradi. SHuningdek, bu yondashuv haqidagi ba'zi noto'g'ri tushunchalar va ularning sabablari yoritib beriladi.

Tayanch so'z va iboralar: til o'qitishga kommunikativ yondashuv, kommunikativ kompetentsiya, nazariy o'rganish, keng o'zlashtirish, grammatika-tarjima metodi, til o'rgapish bosqichlari, grammatikani e'tibordan chetda qoldirish, og'zaki muloqot, yozma muloqot.

КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД В ОБУЧЕНИИ ЯЗЫКУ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена преподавания языков коммуникативно и излагаются преимущества этого подхода в обучении. Кроме того, некоторые неверные представления о коммуникативного подхода представлены и их причины описаны.

Ключевые слова и выражения: коммуникативный подход к обучению языков, коммуникативная компетенция, изучение теоретично, овладение, грамматико-переводной метод, этапы изучения языка, игнорировать грамматику, устное общение, письменное общение.

COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING THE LANGUAGE TO YOUNGER SCHOOLCHILDREN

Abstract. This article focuses on the communicative language teaching and outlines advantages of this approach in teaching and learning. Moreover, some misconceptions about the communicative approach are presented and their reasons are described.

Key words and expressions: communicative approach to teaching languages, communicative competence, learning and acquiring, grammar-translation method, stages of language learning, oral communication, written communication.

O'zbekistonda chet tillarini o'qitish tizimida ulkan o'zgarishlar amalga oshirildi. Chunki kichik maktab yoshidan boshlab, tilni pragmatik asosda o'rganish, o'quvchilarga ruhiy, hissiy ta'sir ko'rsatish orqali til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish bo'yicha ma'lum tajribalar vujudga keldi. Bu esa ta'lim sohasida olib borilayotgan islohotlarning muhim bosqichlaridan biri bo'lib, o'sib kelayotgan avlodni barkamol shaxs qilib tarbiyalashda, ularning jahon standartlari bo'yicha ta'lim olishida ayniqsa ahamiyatlidir.

Ma'lumki, chet tillarini o'rganishda kommunikatsiya jarayoni, kommunikativ kompetentsiya muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu qarorda belgilangan izchil maqsadni amalga oshirish uchun chet tillarini o'rgatishni kommunikativ asosda olib borish katta samara beradi.

Bu tizimga chet tili o'qitishga kommunikativ yondashuv o'tgan asrning oxirlaridan boshlab olib kirildi. O'zbekistonda esa ushbu yangicha uslub XXI asrning boshlaridan joriy etila boshlandi

va o'zining muayyan natijalarini berib kelmoqda. Bunga sabab esa til o'qitishga kommunikativ yondashuvning o'ziga xos afzalliklaridir.

Shulardan birinchisi va, eng muhimi, bu uslub til o'rganuvchining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini shakllantirishga qaratilganligidir. Har qanday tilni o'rganishdan maqsad ushbu tilni amaliyotda qo'llay olish, mazkur til egalari yoki shu tilda muloqot olib boradigan boshqa millat vakillari bilan xoh og'zaki, xoh yozma tarzda suhbat qila olishdan iboratdir. Kommunikativ yondashuv esa til o'rganuvchilarni xuddi shu hayotiy vaziyatlarga tayyorlashni targ'ib qiladi va shuning uchun ham chet tillarini o'rgatish sohasidagi tadqiqotchilar tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanib kelmoqda.

Ikkinchidan esa, ushbu yondashuv chet tilini nazariy asosda *o'rganish* bilan birga, uni amaliy tatbiqi, keng *o'zlashtirishga* e'tibor qaratadi. Bilamizki, til o'zlashtirish jarayonini har bir shaxs o'z ona tilida so'zlashishga o'rganish mobaynida boshidan kechiradi, ya'ni hali bola tili chiqmasdan turib muayyan nutq ifodalarini doimo yaqinlari tomonidan eshitadi, qulog'i shu tilga o'rganadi, ma'lum sezgilar orqali so'zlar ma'nosini anglay boshlaydi, shu so'zlarga taqlid qilib tovushlar, keyinchalik so'zlar talaffuz qila boshlaydi va ma'lum vaqtga yetib bu tilda bemalol gapira, boshqacha aytganda, muloqot qila boshlaydi. Buning uchun bolaga o'z ona tilining grammatik qoidalarini o'rganish yoki so'zlar va ularning ma'nolarini yod olish zarurati bo'lmagan, bularni unga hech kim bevosita o'rgatishi kuzatilmaydi.

Kommunikativ yondashuv ham chet tili o'rganuvchilarni turli hayotiy vaziyatlar, holatlar asosida ma'lum sharoitda chet tilidan qanday foydalanishga o'rgatadi. Ya'ni bunda o'qituvchi o'rganuvchilarga chet tilidagi ma'lum bir hodisalarni ularni o'zlashtirish muhitini yaratib berish orqali o'rgatadi.

Bundan ko'rinadiki, kommunikativ til o'rgatish usuli mamlakatimizda bir necha o'n yilliklar davomida qo'llanib kelingan grammatika-tarjima metodidan tubdan farq qiladi. Ma'lumki, bu uslubda chet tili o'rganuvchilar mazkur chet tilining grammatikasini o'rganishgan, ushbu grammatik birlikdan foydalanib gaplar tuzishgan, turli mashqlar bajarishgan; ushbu tildagi lug'aviy birliklarni yod olishgan va ulardan foydalanib chet tilidan ona tiliga, ona tilidan chet tiliga tarjimalarni amalga oshirishgan. Oqibatda ular chet tilining grammatikasini a'lo darajada bilishgan, so'z boylıkları yetarli bo'lgan, tarjima nazariyasini puxta egallashgan, zarur hayotiy vaziyatlarda esa chet tilini qo'llashda qator to'siqlarga duch kelishgan, katta qiyinchilik bilan mazkur tilda muloqotga kirishishgan. Bunday muammolarga sabab ular tilni quruq o'rganishgan, ya'ni uni amaliy jihatdan o'zlashtirishmagan.

Shuningdek, kommunikativ til o'rgatish o'rganuvchilardan tilni bosqichma-bosqich o'rganishni targ'ib qiladi. Bosqichlar sifatida esa til birliklaridan ijodiy foydalanish, uni sinab ko'rish va ma'lum vaziyatlarda xatolarga yo'l qo'yish tushuniladi. Xatolarga yo'l qo'yish til o'zlashtirishning me'yoriy holatidir, lekin muloqot kompetentsiyasi rivojlanib borgani sari til o'rganuvchida mazkur tilni ravon va xatosiz ishlatish ko'nikmalari shakllanib boradi.

Boshqacha aytganda, chet tili o'qitishga kommunikativ yondashuv til o'rganish jarayonini mazmunli, samarali bo'lishini ta'minlaydi.

Yuqoridagi va shu kabi boshqa afzalliklarga ega bo'lgan kommunikativ til o'qitish uslubi ko'plab chet tili o'qitish guruhlarida muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanmoqda. Biroq ushbu yondashuvni talqin qilishda ba'zi kamchiliklar mavjudki, bu holat ayrim o'qituvchilar tomonidan o'z

mashg'ulotlarini tashkillashda xatoliklarga yo'l qo'yishga sabab bo'lmoqda va ta'lim sifatiga salbiy ta'sirini ko'rsatmoqda.

Shunday noto'g'ri tushunchalardan biri, ayni vaqtda, eng ko'p tarqalgani kommunikativ yondashuvda grammatikani e'tibordan chetda qoldirish sanaladi. Bunday talqin grammatika-tarjima metodining kamchiliklarini nazarda tutgan holda yuzaga kelgan. Mazkur g'oya grammatikani kommunikativ yondashuv asosida to'g'ri o'rgatishni chuqur anglamagan ayrim mutaxassislar uchun qo'l kelmoqda. Shuningdek, chet tili o'rganuvchilarda ham chet tilini bilish uchun, o'sha tilda muloqot qilish uchun grammatikani o'rganishga ehtiyoj yo'q degan xato fikrning uyg'onishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Aslida esa chet tilining grammatikasini bilmasdan turib ushbu tilni mukammal egallash mumkin emas. Kommunikativ til o'qitish esa og'zaki va yozma muloqot orqali til o'rganuvchilarda grammatik kompetentsiyani shakllantirishni nazarda tutadi.

Kommunikativ yondashuv haqidagi yana bir noto'g'ri qarash ushbu uslub faqat gapirishga, ya'ni og'zaki muloqotga o'rgatadi, degan fikrdir. Bunday xato fikrga sabab ko'pgina holatlarda o'rganuvchilar chet tilidan xorijliklar bilan og'zaki muloqotga kirishish uchun foydalanishlaridir. SHu tufayli chet tili darslarida o'rganuvchilarning so'zlash va eshitib tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiruvchi topshiriqlar muhim bo'lib qolmoqda. Biroq muloqot ikki kishi o'rtasidagi og'zaki va yozma munosabatni ko'zda tutadi.

Shunday ekan, har xil rasmiy va norasmiy xatlar, ish qog'ozlari, hattoki, mobil telefon yoki internet tarmoqlarida jo'natilayotgan xabarlar ham muloqotning o'ziga xos shakllaridir. Kommunikativ til o'qitishda ham o'rganuvchilarning yozma nutqlarini, shu bilan birga, o'qib tushunish ko'nikmalarini o'stirish ta'limdan ko'zda tutilgan maqsadlardandir.

Shu va shu kabi boshqa noto'g'ri qarashlar¹ chet tili o'qitishga kommunikativ yondashuvning ba'zan yetarli darajada samara bermasligiga olib kelmoqda. Shunday ekan, biror usulni qo'llashda uning mohiyatini chuqur anglash, uni noto'g'ri talqin qilmaslik mazkur uslubning samaradorligini ta'minlashini unutmasligimiz lozimdir.

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